

EHDEN

EUROPEAN HEALTH DATA & EVIDENCE NETWORK

806968 – EHDEN

European Health Data & Evidence Network

WP1 – Evidence Workflow Development

D1.1 Report on key data source/s of interest for WP1 Use Cases

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DOCUMENT HISTORY

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V1.3	29/05/2019	Final version after review

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DEFINITIONS

Participants of the EHDEN Consortium are referred to herein according to the following codes:

EMC	Erasmus Medical Center Rotterdam- The Netherlands (Project Coordinator)
Synapse	Synapse Research Management Partners S.L. - Spain
UOXF	The Chancellor, Masters and Scholars of the University of Oxford - United Kingdom
UTARTU	Tartu Ulikool - Estonia
UAVR	Universidade de Aveiro – Portugal
The Hyve	The Hyve BV – the Netherlands
Odysseus	Odysseus Data Services SRO – Czech Republic
EPF	Forum Europeen des Patients (FPE) - Luxembourg
NICE	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence – United Kingdom
UMC	Stiftelsen WHO Collaborating Centre for International Drug Monitoring - Sweden
ICHOM	International Consortium for Health Outcomes measurement LTD - United Kingdom
Janssen	Janssen Pharmaceutica NV - Belgium (Project Lead)
Pfizer	Pfizer Limited – United Kingdom
Abbvie	AbbVie Inc - United States
IRIS	Institut De Recherches Internationales Servier - France
SARD	Sanofi Aventis Recherche & Developpement - France
Bayer	Bayer Aktiengesellschaft - Germany
Lilly	Eli Lilly and Company Limited – United Kingdom
AZ	AstraZeneca AB - Sweden
Novartis	Novartis Pharma AG - Switzerland
UCB	UCB Biopharma SPRL - Belgium
Celgene	Celgene Management SARL - Switzerland

Grant agreement	The agreement signed between the beneficiaries and the IMI JU for the undertaking of the EHDEN project (806968).
Project	The sum of all activities carried out in the framework of the Grant Agreement.
Consortium	The EHDEN Consortium, comprising the above-mentioned legal entities.
Consortium agreement	Agreement concluded amongst EHDEN participants for the implementation of the Grant Agreement. Such an agreement shall not affect the parties' obligations to the Community and/or to one another arising from the Grant Agreement.

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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

EHDEN aims to build a large-scale, federated network of data sources standardized to a common data model. The choice of data sources to be prioritised will be driven by a number of motivations. Workpackage 1 contributes to this process by providing insights into the type of data needed for the proposed use cases that affect WP1, in collaboration with WP3. In addition, WP2 has identified key priority areas in D2.1, which are also considered here.

The two use cases agreed by the contributing partners to date are drug utilization studies (Use Case 1) and regulatory research into the safety of drugs and devices (Use Case 2). A third Use Case (Use Case 3) will focus on health technology assessments, which will be led by WP2. With these in mind, discussions have been held in a face-to-face meeting and in the form of teleconferences. Protocols for both use cases have been drafted in collaboration with members of WP1, WP2 and WP3, and recently submitted to data access committees relevant to two data custodians. In addition, two key therapeutic areas have been selected as part of D2.1 (see D2.1 report), namely prostate cancer and inflammatory arthritis.

The data required for the use cases in the short-term include electronic medical records, health registers, and/or claims data. In addition, we recognize the need for alternative data sources for future use cases and for studies in key priority areas identified by WP2, to include: drug/s (biologic therapies for inflammatory arthritis and chemotherapy/ies for prostate cancer) and/or disease (cancer, arthritis) registers. Finally, additional data sources might be needed in future use cases, including device registers.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The overarching aim of EHDEN is to build a large-scale, federated network of data sources standardized to the OMOP common data model. WP1 has worked with members of the consortium, particularly with leads of WP2 (Outcome Driven Healthcare) and WP3 (Personalized Medicine), to design use cases that will test the platform, and drive the development of analytical and visualization tools to be used in the EHDEN network.

After a face-to-face meeting and a number of teleconferences and protocol writing, three generic use cases have been proposed, namely:

- **Use Case 1: Drug Utilisation Studies:** protocols have been prepared and submitted to data custodians from two countries (UK and the Netherlands) to perform a number of drug utilisation studies during the coming 3-4 years. The first one included is a study on the use of respiratory drugs for asthma and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD). Once implemented and tested, the development of tools for DUS will enable rapid monitoring of population- and patient-level drug use, including the measuring of the effect of risk minimisation strategies through the EHDEN network to improve regulatory decision-making at a European level.
- **Use Case 2: Drug and device safety / Regulatory:** Post-authorisation safety studies (PASS) are currently common as part of regulatory risk minimisation plans since 2012. Recently, a new EU regulation was approved for the approval of medical devices in Europe. EHDEN will maximise the efficiency of drug safety PASS delivery whilst developing a much needed European framework for device epidemiology. As part of this, a number of statistical methods will be explored in a number of pharmaco- and/or medical device research scenarios to provide guidance on best analytical methods for each different research question. The proposed use cases will take an iterative approach with the following three steps:
 1. Signal detection: Signals from spontaneous reporting systems will be identified using existing methods by the UMC participants using the World Health Organization VigiBase database for the first two years of EHDEN. In following years, the same algorithms for signal detection will be applied to real world data mapped to the OMOP common data model in EHDEN.
 2. Adverse effect confirmation and further research: Safety signals identified in 1 will be tested in OMOP-mapped data using state-of-the-art analytical methods to include propensity score matching and self-controlled case series.
 3. Prediction of adverse effects: Adverse drug/device effects identified in 1 and confirmed in 2 will be the outcome/s for patient prediction modelling in collaboration with WP3. The aim of this task is to provide clinicians and researchers with algorithms for the identification of drug/device users/recipients at high risk of a given (newly identified) unwanted effect.
- **Use Case 3: Health Technology Assessment/s.** The protocols for this Use Case are in development, and will include the study of health resource use and patient reported outcomes. A first clinical study will study healthcare resource use associated with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), and others will follow, likely in line with the clinical areas of interest chosen for WP2 (see below).

These three Use Cases have driven the identification of some of the relevant data sources outlined below. Additional Use Cases developed during the EHDEN project lifetime will likely require additional data, and will be reported upon in due course.

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In addition to the use cases, WP2 has identified two key priority areas for further research, as detailed in report D2.1:

- Prostate cancer
- Inflammatory arthritis

These will require the inclusion of additional data sources for future research to ensure completeness of information on patient characteristics, disease features, treatment/s (including in-hospital chemotherapy and/or biologic therapies), and patient reported outcomes.

2. METHODS

2.1 Data source identification for the proposed UCs

The overarching aim of the proposed UCs is to test and develop cross-country, reproducible, efficient drug utilisation, drug/device safety, and health technology assessment analyses.

Members of WP1 and WP3 will co-lead UC1 and 2, in collaboration with WP4 for the development of re-usable analytical and data visualization tools. The WP2 lead will lead on UC3.

The identification of data sources relevant to all three use cases started during a face-to-face meeting in Rotterdam, and continued during follow-up teleconferences and through the development of a first study protocol for all three. The process for the identification of relevant data sources was high level (e.g. type of data), rather than formal or specific (e.g. a specific data source). In addition, future UCs are likely to appear during the lifetime of the EHDEN project, which might require different data.

2.2 Data source identification for priority clinical/therapeutic areas

In addition to the data needs for the proposed use cases, we have considered input from WP2 on relevant clinical/therapeutic areas. The information and methods used for the selection of key priority areas is detailed in D2.1 report. The selected priority areas are prostate cancer and inflammatory arthritis.

3. RESULTS

Use Case 1 and 2 have confirmed the need for data sources containing detailed information on drug prescriptions/dispensations, as well as on relevant patient features for characterization and for the identification of relevant clinical outcomes (for safety analyses and prediction modelling). Table 1 summarizes the need for data domains and potential sources of data needed for these two use cases.

Table 1.- Data needs and relevant data source types (high level) needed for UC1 (DUS) and UC2 (Regulatory)

Data domain/s needs	Potential data source types				
	Primary care EMR	Hospital records/EMR	Claims	Drug/device register	Disease registry
Drugs (prescriptions/dispensing)	*	*	+	+	*
Devices (claims or procedure code/s)	-	*	*	+	*
Patient characteristics	+	+	+	*	*

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Clinical outcomes/events	+	+	+	*	+
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NOTE: + = expected complete information; * = expected incomplete information or variable; - = no/little or insufficient data for the proposed use cases

Based on this information, primary care EMR, hospital records/EMR/registers and claims data are seen as the short-term priority data sources for UC1 and UC2. We recognise the need for the study of drugs or devices not always recorded in EMR or claims data, including hospital-dispensed therapies or specific device types. Future use cases will therefore require the use of drug/device and/or disease registers. As for Use Case 3, WP2 has confirmed the need for additional information on health resource utilization (patient contact/s with healthcare system, drug use, etc) as well as on patient reported outcomes. Again, these are likely better recorded in disease and/or drug/device registers, strengthening the need for such data sources in the coming 1-2 years of EHDEN.

As detailed above, the other motivation for the identification of relevant data sources is the conducting of research in key priority areas identified in D2.1, namely prostate cancer and inflammatory arthritis. Table 2 summarizes specific data needs for these, and potential data sources for research in such clinical areas.

Table 2.- Data needs and relevant data source types (high level) needed for key priority areas identified by WP2 (prostate cancer and inflammatory arthritis)

	Primary care EMR	Hospital records/EMR	Claims	Drug register	Disease registry
Cancer therapies	-	*	*	+	+
Biologics and small molecule therapies	-	*	*	+	+
Disease stage/severity	-	*	-	+	+
Clinical outcomes	+	+	+	*	+
Patient reported outcomes	-	*	-	*	*

NOTE: + = expected complete information; * = expected incomplete information or variable; - = no/little or insufficient data for the proposed use cases

Based on this information, drug (biologics, cancer treatments) and disease (arthritis and cancer registers) will be needed for future studies in these priority areas as part of EHDEN.

4. DISCUSSION

The proposed Use Cases are in line with those proposed in the DoA. These will be disease-agnostic, but specific areas will be covered in bespoke clinical examples driven by members of WP1, WP2 and WP3. The data sources needed for the completion of the first Use Cases include:

- Primary care EMR
- Hospital records/registers/EMR
- Claims data

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Additional Use Cases will be conducted as part of EHDEN, that will require additional/alternative data sources, namely:

- Drug registers
- Device registers

In parallel, WP2 has identified prostate cancer and inflammatory arthritis as two key priority areas as detailed in D2.1 report. Additional data sources will be needed for future research into these clinical areas:

- Biologic therapy/ies registers
- Cancer treatment/s registers
- Arthritis registers
- Cancer registers

5. NEXT STEPS

We have identified a list of data sources needed for the completion of the proposed short- and mid-term use cases, and for research into key therapeutic areas identified by WP2. This information will be communicated to the relevant WPs for prioritisation during the upcoming short- and mid-term data source grant calls.

The list of data sources to be prioritised in the short-term (first year of EHDEN) is:

- EMR (primary care and/or hospital)
- Claims

In the mid-term (second and possibly third year of EHDEN) additional data sources will be needed:

- Drug registers, and in particular biologic and cancer treatment registers
- Disease registers, and in particular arthritis and cancer registers
- Device registers

The next deliverable from WP1 is the final study protocols for the proposed "proof-of-concept" studies (aka use cases), which is required for Month 24. Protocols specific to two known data custodians have been submitted to their respective data access committees, and approved by one of them. Blanket (data source agnostic) protocols are being prepared, and will be ready before the proposed deadline.